

ATYPICAL LOCALIZATIONS OF ECHINOCOCCOSIS – A SYNTHETIC REVIEW

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Abstract

Echinococcosis is a parasitic zoonosis caused by the larval forms of the genus *Echinococcus*, particularly *E. granulosus* and *E. multilocularis*, representing a major public health concern in endemic regions [3,5]. The liver ($\approx 70\%$) and lungs ($\approx 20\%$) are the classical sites of infection [4,7]. In 10–15% of cases, atypical localizations occur, presenting with nonspecific clinical manifestations and significant diagnostic challenges [6,14]. Accurate diagnosis and appropriate management are essential to prevent severe complications [1,10].

Keywords: echinococcosis, atypical localizations

INTRODUCTION

Cystic echinococcosis is a helminthic infection caused by the larval stage of *Echinococcus granulosus*, with humans acting as accidental intermediate hosts [4]. Transmission occurs through ingestion of eggs shed by the definitive host, most commonly the dog [5].

After penetrating the intestinal mucosa, hexacanth embryos enter the portal circulation and are predominantly retained in the liver. Some larvae bypass the hepatic and pulmonary filters and reach the systemic circulation, resulting in extrahepatic and extrapulmonary localizations [6,14].

The currently recommended imaging classification is that proposed by the WHO-IWGE [1,25].

Atypical localizations occur through:

- bypassing the hepato-pulmonary filter [6]
- systemic hematogenous dissemination [14]
- lymphatic spread
- spontaneous or traumatic rupture of a primary cyst [11]
- intraoperative iatrogenic dissemination [19]

ATYPICAL LOCALIZATIONS

Cerebral localization - occurs in 1–2% of cases, more frequently in children and adolescents [8]. Clinically, it presents with signs of intracranial hypertension, seizures, and focal neurological deficits [8,18]. CT and MRI reveal a well-defined cystic lesion with cerebrospinal fluid-like content [13,18]. Treatment is surgical (Dowling-Orlando technique), combined with albendazole therapy [1,8].

Cardiac localization - represents 0.5–2% of cases [9,17]. The left ventricle is most commonly affected [17]. Clinical manifestations include chest pain, arrhythmias, dyspnea, or syncope [9].

Severe complications may occur, such as systemic embolism, intrapericardial rupture, and cardiac tamponade [17]. Diagnosis is based on echocardiography and cardiac MRI [9].

Treatment consists of surgical excision under extracorporeal circulation, associated with antihelminthic therapy [1,17].

Osseous localization - occurs in 0.5–4% of cases [12]. The vertebrae, pelvis, and long bones are most frequently involved [12]. The lesion has an infiltrative pattern without formation of a well-defined pericyst, mimicking malignant pathology [6]. Clinically, it presents with chronic pain and pathological fractures [12]. Prognosis is guarded due to frequent recurrences [12].

Splenic localization - accounts for 2–6% of cases [20]. Clinically presents with splenomegaly and left upper quadrant pain [20]. Imaging findings are similar to those of hepatic localization [13]. Standard treatment is splenectomy or selective spleen-preserving surgery [20].

Renal localization - incidence ranges between 2–4% [21]. The pathognomonic sign is hydatiduria, which is rarely observed [21]. Differential diagnosis includes cystic renal tumors and complicated urinary infections [21]. Treatment is surgical, preferably organ-preserving when feasible [21].

Muscular and subcutaneous localization - represents 1–3% of cases [14,24]. It presents as a painless, slowly progressive mass [24]. Differential diagnosis includes sarcoma and cold abscess [6]. Treatment consists of complete surgical excision [1].

Peritoneal localization - usually secondary to rupture of a hepatic cyst [11]. May cause ascites and multiple intra-abdominal dissemination [15]. The major complication is anaphylactic reaction [11].

Pancreatic localization - is rare (0.2–2%) [22]. The pancreatic head is most commonly involved, leading to obstructive jaundice [22]. May present with epigastric pain or pancreatitis [22]. Differential diagnosis includes pancreatic pseudocyst and cystic

neoplasms [22]. Treatment is surgical, tailored to localization, combined with albendazole therapy [1,22].

Thyroid localization – is extremely rare (<1%) [23]. Presents as a painless thyroid nodule, usually with normal thyroid function [23]. Differential diagnosis includes simple thyroid cyst and cystic carcinoma [23]. Fine-needle aspiration is controversial due to the risk of dissemination [23]. Treatment consists of lobectomy or partial thyroidectomy [1,23].

Diagnosis

Imaging (ultrasound, CT, MRI) is essential for identifying lesions and classifying them according to WHO-IWGE criteria [1,25].

Serology (ELISA, Western blot) shows variable sensitivity, lower in isolated localizations [3,5].

Treatment

Combined surgical and medical treatment (albendazole 10–15 mg/kg/day) is recommended in most cases [1,10].

The PAIR technique is reserved for selected situations [1].

CONCLUSION

Atypical localizations of echinococcosis represent a major diagnostic challenge, as they may mimic neoplastic or inflammatory diseases [6,14]. In endemic areas, echinococcosis should be included in the differential diagnosis of any atypical cystic lesion. Multidisciplinary management and adherence to international guidelines are essential to reduce morbidity and mortality [1,3].

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